

EMC2 Annual Report Year 1

November 2024

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.19697568

See the [CHECKLIST](#) on the final page!

⚠ Please note that you can only fill in the form fields, all other content is blocked. For automatic evaluation purposes, please ensure that you submit the report as a **Word document**. You can submit a pdf in addition.

Driving Urban Transitions Partnership (DUT)

Project Progress Report

CONTENT

- 1. KEY DATA OF THE PROJECT2
- 2. DESCRIPTION OF WORK, OBJECTIVES AND (PRELIMINARY) RESULTS.....2
- 3. IMPACT5
- 4. DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION ACTIVITIES9
- 5. OUTLOOK10
- 6. PROJECT ORGANISATION AND MANAGEMENT12
- 7. YOUR COMMENTS FOR THE DUT PARTNERSHIP13
- 8. ELECTRONIC SIGNATURE13
- 9. FORMALITIES CHECKLIST14

1. KEY DATA OF THE PROJECT

SHORT TITLE: EMC2

LONG TITLE: The Evolutive Meshed Compact City. A pragmatic transition pathway to the 15-minute City for European metropolitan peripheries.

PROJECT NUMBER: F-DUT-2022-0043

YEAR OF CALL: DUT Call 2022

PROJECT START: 01/10/2023

PROJECT END: 31/10/2026

PROJECT COORDINATOR: Giovanni FUSCO

NUMBER OF REPORT: Annual Report 1

REPORTING PERIOD: from 01/10/2023 to 31/10/2024

1.1 Publishable Project Summary (max. 2 pages) - *only for the Final Project Report*

[INFO: Your text should be easy to read, that is, written in an understandable and accessible way for a broader public. Its purpose should aim to promote the dissemination and support the exploitation of your results. You should refer only to publicly available information and must not include any confidential or personal data (e.g. names and addresses). The Publishable Project Summary must be drafted as a "stand-alone" text. No references should be made to other parts of the report. You may also wish to provide diagrams or photographs illustrating and promoting the work of your project (only as images). Please structure your summary along the following sub-sections:

- *Context and overall objectives*
- *Work performed and main achievements*
- *Results and socio-economic impacts*
- *Policy relevance of your project]*

Klicken oder tippen Sie hier, um Text einzugeben.

2. DESCRIPTION OF WORK, OBJECTIVES AND (PRELIMINARY) RESULTS

2.1 Project Progress in the Reporting Period

Is the project progressing as planned and as described in the proposal?

YES

If NO, please explain the reasons therefore in Chapter 2.2 below (deficiencies, risks and bottlenecks).

2.2 Description of Work (max. 3 pages)

- **What are the most important objectives you have accomplished (in line with the ones listed in the Online Survey) in the reporting period?**

- **Please describe the work accomplished in the reporting period, structured according to the work packages. Describe the preliminary innovations and results as indicated in the Online Survey (Product/service/process/policy/social innovations).**
- **Describe how you have worked together with the main target group(s)/stakeholder(s); describe your experiences and key takeaways (please refer to interactions with the urban actors included in the Online Survey).**
- **Describe deficiencies, risks and bottlenecks in the project progress. Describe deviations from the proposed work plan, deliverables and milestones, if any. What helped you or would have helped you to overcome these issues?**

The first year of the project was marked by a significant effort in establishing both the administrative and scientific infrastructure: drafting and signing the Consortium Agreement, preparing an initial version of the Data Management Plan, creating a shared platform for project data and documents, launching the project website, and recruiting postdoctoral researchers and PhD candidates. Within this framework, the Consortium actively pursued the scheduled activities.

Overall, the achievement of project objectives aligns with the original timeline, with a slight delay in WP2 compensated by ahead-of-schedule progress in WP5. Work on WP5 also provided an opportunity to engage stakeholders earlier than planned. The main preliminary results of the project within year 1 are the full specification of the EMC2 model (WP1), the development of original analytical protocols at the metropolitan scale (WP2, even if they are not all finalized) and the catalog of historical linear settlements in the metropolitan areas of France (Lille-Roubaix-Tourcoing and the French Riviera) and Austria (Vienna), which can serve as starting point for the emc2 model of the 15-minute city in metropolitan peripheries.

A key development during the project's first year was the expansion of the consortium to include a fifth urban authority, which will be formalized at the upcoming General Assembly in December 2024. The city of Massa will join the city of Viareggio as a cooperation partner in Italy, alongside the city of Gothenburg in Sweden and the two Planning Agencies of Lille and the French Riviera in France, the latter being a co-applicant of the project.

The progress of the six main work packages (WPs) is detailed below, with some adjustments to the scheduled deliverables.

WP1. Objective: Define the key characteristics of the EMC2 model as a practical application of the 15mC concept in the peripheries of European metropolitan areas, and evaluate the model based on the research project's outcomes.

Status of implementation 70 % (as scheduled): the general characteristics of the EMC2 model were determined through literature review, evaluation of theoretical layouts and collective discussion among consortium partners. It was decided to renounce the online survey, because it was to be conducted within France only and its contribution to model development was limited.

The EMC2 model specification is a first product innovation, requiring further innovations within the project (analytical protocols, assessment and intervention guidelines) and beyond it (policies).

Deliverables and Milestones of the period:

D1.1 Working paper on model specifications and D1.2 Working paper on different theoretical layouts: done and stored on the EMC2 Sharedocs platform.

M1. Collective validation of general specification of EMC2 model and assessment of theoretical layouts: achieved.

D1.3 Diagrams and results of survey: not done because consortium decided to cancel the survey

D1.4 Draft journal paper presenting the EMC2 model specification: done (proceedings AESOP 2024)

WP2. Objective: Assess the potential of the EMC2 model in the peripheries of selected European metropolitan areas through the implementation of innovative analytical protocols of the street network, of built-up forms, of functions and of accessible population.

Status of implementation 30 % (50% scheduled): protocols of population analysis were produced (T2.3). Protocols for main street identification are in progress including an analytical protocol to assess the multimodal mobility network and applied to the city of Gothenburg; the analysis of its connection to the network of main streets is underway (T2.1). The protocols for morphological and function analysis are under way and forthcoming (T2.2 and T2.3). First maps of results (T2.4) were produced for population analysis. Identification of main streets, morphological characteristics and functions are to come in year 2, as well as a draft journal paper on combined protocols and comparative analysis of the study areas. Given the foreseen entrance in the consortium of a second urban authority of the Versilia metropolitan area (the city of Massa), it was decided to renounce to the metropolitan area of Florence, where no urban authority entered the consortium, and to implement the analyses on 5 metropolitan areas: Lille-Roubaix-Tourcoing and the French Riviera (France), Gothenburg (Sweden), Vienna (Austria) and Versilia (Italy). The protocols and assessment maps of WP2 will be main product and service innovations. Meetings are scheduled with urban actors within the consortium to, based on the cross-sectional analysis, discuss the variation in potential of implementation of the EMC2 model in metropolitan peripheries.

Deliverables and Milestones of the period:

D2.1 Analytical protocol to identify the foreground street network. In progress (delayed month 14)

D2.2 Analytical protocol to assess the build-up forms on street networks. In progress (delayed m 14)

D2.3 Analytical protocol to assess services on street network (delayed month 16)

D2.4 Analytical protocol to assess population around the street network. Done and accessible on Github.

WP3. Objective: Identify traditional linear settlements within selected European metropolitan areas and understand their historical formation and transformation to assess their capacity to act as starting point of the EMC2 model.

Status of implementation 60 % (as scheduled): The catalog of historical linear settlements was produced for Vienna, Lille-Roubaix-Tourcoing, the Versilia Conurbation and the French Riviera. A specific challenge was the different analytical approaches developed by researchers at TUW and at CNRS-ESPACE. The consortium took advantage of this diversity by carrying the analysis of the French Riviera case study with both methods, which allowed the identification of analogies and differences in methods and outcomes. The diachronic analysis of street networks in Gothenburg and Vienna is underway, as well as in Versilia, which was added to the original project.

Deliverables and Milestones of the period:

3.1 Catalog of historical linear settlements in the study areas. Done and stored on the EMC2 Sharedocs

3.2 A: This work is mainly carried out by SMOG, for the diachronic analysis of the entire road network of Vienna the data basis was collected and transmitted by TUW-DU, as well as by DESTeC for the diachronic analysis of the grid configuration of the Versilia conurbation. The work is done and stored on the EMC2 Sharedocs.

WP4. Objective: Assess the relations of the network of main streets with green/blue networks and with mobility networks.

Status of implementation 10 % (as scheduled): A PhD candidate was recruited to develop an agent-based model of pedestrian mobility in Drap (French Riviera). A conceptual framework for the model was produced and the PhD candidate received the necessary training. A PhD candidate was also recruited to analyze the blue & green networks in Gothenburg (starting date November 1, 2024). The models and protocols of WP4 are substantial product and service innovations and associate the French Riviera Planning Agency and the City of Gothenburg in their development. Further collaboration is scheduled for the assessment of planning scenarios in years 2 and 3. No deliverables or milestones were scheduled for this period.

WP5. Objective: Assess the fine-grained forms and functions of test areas within European metropolitan peripheries and propose possible transformations to implement the EMC2 model.

Status of implementation: 20 % (0% scheduled): The start of WP5 (June 2024) was brought forward from the original project timeline. Test areas were identified in the French Riviera, Lille-Roubaix-Tourcoing, Versilia using preliminary findings of WP2 and WP3, and in close collaboration with the French Riviera Planning Agency, the Lille Metropolitan Planning Agency, the cities of Massa and Viareggio. Identification of test areas is in progress in Vienna. Protocols for fine-grained assessments were produced and a first implementation was done on the test area of Drap (French Riviera). Work is under way for 3D-models in the test area of the French Riviera and is planned for next year in Vienna and Lille-Roubaix-Tourcoing. No deliverables were scheduled for the period.

WP6. Objective: Produce assessment and interventions guidelines and assess their compatibility with present regulations. Provide methods to generalize local findings.

Status of implementation 0% (as scheduled): The start of WP6 is foreseen for month 18 and will involve close collaboration within the four research teams and the four urban authorities within the consortium.

3. IMPACT

3.1 Impact of the Project (*max. 1.5 pages*)

- **What is your project's contribution to urban transitions (societal, economic, cultural and environmental changes) that you would like to highlight as an achievement so far?**
- **How is that linked to the DUT Roadmap¹ and to the DUT Transition Pathway(s)? Please ensure consistency with your answer on *Contribution to the Transition Pathway Missions* in the Online Survey.**
- **What is your project's expected impact in a long-term perspective, both in terms of urban transitions and regarding the DUT Roadmap and the relevant Transition Pathway(s)? Which actions do you plan to take for reaching the expected impact?**

¹ Document can be found at <https://dutpartnership.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/09/DUT-Roadmap-2022-komprimiert.pdf>

[INFO: Be as concrete as possible, for example: "establishing a good citizen interaction with the urban planning department in terms of gentrification" or "municipality is using a strategy or an app for upkeeping the green in the city".]

The model of the Evolutive Meshed Compact City tackles conjointly the three topics of the 15mC proposed by the DUT call. Even more, it maintains that there is added value in treating the three topics together while recognizing the constraints and opportunities of our networked metropolitan areas. Thus, strengthening the mix of urban functions and services needs morphological (the streetscape potential, with its buildings and their interfaces to the public space) and configurational pre-conditions (the centrality potential of the street network, shaping flows of through-traffic, both pedestrian and vehicular), includes access to transit networks and benefits from attractive public spaces, to be viable over time. By concentrating on main streets, the stronger mix of retail and services within the EMC2 model will produce synergies and increase the attractiveness of the main streets which, by design, will allow for a rich variety of usages by pedestrians, resulting in vibrant public life on the backbone of the surrounding neighborhoods. Our project is linked to the DUT roadmap by identifying and comprehending the spatial synergies between the infrastructures that together make the 15mC work. The protocols developed within the project allow thematic exchange between metropolitan areas, provide common formats and methods and as such contribute to evidence-driven actions and policies.

The project contributes to two of the four Key Areas (KA) identified in the DUT roadmap. First, it contributes to the DUT vision for urban mobility transformation, where traffic planning is integrated into comprehensive and strategic urban planning and considers different mobility needs. Second, EMC2 starts from the understanding that the built environment fundamentally predetermines mobility options, because all urban movement takes place within the streetscape, which in turn is shaped and defined by buildings and the urban morphology. The protocols developed within EMC2 provide methods to include urban morphology in the decision-making process and evidence-driven action.

By establishing an alternative model for the 15-minute city in European metropolitan peripheries, the project contributes to reach more general goals outlined in the EU Soil Strategy for 2030, or the 11.7 objective of the goal 11 'Make cities inclusive, safe, resilient and sustainable' of the UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs): 'provide universal access to safe, inclusive and accessible, green and public spaces, in particular for women and children, older persons and persons with disabilities'. Scaling, replication and mainstreaming of project outcomes, protocols and guidelines, will be instrumental in attaining these ambitious goals (see next section).

3.2 Scaling, Replication and Mainstreaming (max. 2 pages) - *only for the Final Project Report*

- **Which of your innovative solutions (product / service / process / policy / social innovations) could be mainstreamed / replicated / scaled-out by cities, businesses or other stakeholders?**
- **Which of these innovative solutions could change citizens' behaviour/mind-sets, and how?**
- **Which of these innovative solutions could make an impact on different governance levels / system level if taken up by policymakers and used for political decisions, new/adapted regulations, etc.?**

[INFO: Think about what your project could possibly achieve within 5-10 years, for example: more integrated transport systems, more localised economies, improved resilience and adaptation to extreme events, inclusive societies with respect to migration and ageing.]

Scaling and replication are central objectives of the project. Analyses are conducted on five distinct European metropolitan areas, each evaluated at different scales (both the entire metropolitan area and targeted peripheral test areas). Scaling concerns both the passage from large scale (the whole metropolitan area) to small scale (test areas in metropolitan peripheries) and, reversely, the generalization from the latter to the former. Replication concerns both the possibility to carry out fine-scale analyses in other peripheral districts, as well as in other European metropolitan areas and peripheral districts not covered by the project. The protocols developed, along with the EMC2 model as a whole, offer transferable and replicable outcomes. The project will yield a comprehensive specification of the EMC2 model, protocols to assess its application potential at multiple scales, and actionable guidelines for urban practitioners. These guidelines will support the transformation of existing urban and suburban environments. With only minor physical changes, metropolitan authorities will be able to improve internal connectivity and foster compact urban forms along development corridors. Additionally, the protocols will enable the identification of main streets as vectors for this transformation. A particular emphasis has been given to open science and public availability of produced protocols and outcomes since year 1 and the establishment of the project Data Management Plan.

The EMC2 model, along with its analytical protocols and guidelines, holds significant potential for mainstream adoption by local planning authorities. Specifically, collaboration with urban partners in WP6 will evaluate the intervention guidelines in relation to current regulations, identifying potential barriers to broader implementation. Dissemination and outreach activities will further support this general objective. However, given the project's research-oriented nature, validation of the EMC2 model takes precedence over mainstreaming its guidelines. A subsequent, innovation-focused project may be necessary to address mainstream integration within planning practices more directly.

3.3 Interdisciplinarity / Transdisciplinarity (max. 0.5 page)

Did any new insights arise because of the interdisciplinary or transdisciplinary setup of your project?

[INFO: For example: using a methodology from another discipline; engaging non-academic partners, e.g. civil society, local governance, or business actors, in project activities / tasks]

The project consortium consists of four public research units (ESPACE, SMOG, DESTeC, and TUW-UD) and four public urban authorities (the Cities of Gothenburg and Viareggio, in Sweden and Italy, and the planning agencies AUA and ADULM in France). Additionally, a fifth public authority, the city of Massa in Italy, has requested to join and will officially participate in the project beginning in Year 2.

The research units represent diverse countries and disciplinary fields—geography, urban planning and design, civil engineering, and architecture. Each has a specific focus: Urban Design - TUW specializes in architecture and urban design; ESPACE in geography and planning; DESTeC in engineering and planning; and SMOG in urban design and planning. Despite these distinct disciplines, all units share a foundational interest in urban morphology, supporting interdisciplinary and transdisciplinary collaboration. This morphological perspective is similarly valued by the public authorities involved in the consortium.

Several methodologies act as additional bridges between the research units. Configurational approaches rooted in network analysis are key focal points for SMoG (Sweden) and DESTeC (Italy). Geoprocessing in urban analysis is a defining feature of ESPACE (France) and is also shared by SMoG and DESTeC. Historical urban morphology, a central focus for Urban Design - TUW, resonates through more general morphological research across the other three units. Urban 3D-modeling is a further common area of interest between UD-TUW and ESPACE, even if with different methodological approaches.

Regular transdisciplinary meetings have been held across various work packages (within this first year this was the case for WP1, WP2, WP3, and WP5). Conducted primarily online, these meetings enable consortium members to collaboratively address the multifaceted aspects of each work package, drawing on the consortium's combined expertise and diverse disciplinary knowledge. Two young researchers from UD-TUW and DESTeC were hosted by ESPACE for two weeks in October 2024, to compare approaches in WP5 and acquire new skills in methods of urban analysis based on pattern languages.

Additionally, during the first year, meetings were organized between urban public authorities and academic members, mainly on a national level (e.g., ESPACE with AUA and ADULM; SMoG with the city of Gothenburg; DESTeC with the cities of Viareggio and Massa). These interactions facilitated the exchange of academic research and professional practice with a shared understanding of the national regulatory framework. Moreover, initial transnational meetings have been held, such as between UD-TUW and ADULM, establishing the groundwork for further collaboration between UD-TUW, ESPACE, and the two French planning agencies.

3.4 Experiences from Experimental Approaches, like ULL (if applicable) (max. 1 page)

Describe your activities and experiences from experimental approaches, like Urban Living Labs (ULL), that can facilitate the co-design of radical transitions towards greater liveability in urban areas. How did you engage different target groups, such as local public administrations and residents, businesses, NGOs, civil society organisations, and more?

The EMC2 project did not implement any experimental approaches in Year 1 beyond conducting fieldwork on the test areas of WP3, WP4, and WP5. During this period, the Urban Design team at TUW and the ESPACE team at Université Côte d'Azur organized teaching and research studios. In Vienna, they involved master students of architecture in November 2023-January 2024 and in April-June 2024 at TUW, with the participation of urban actors (city of Vienna, the professional association IG Architektur) and of members of ESPACE from France. In Nice, they involved master students in geography and international master students in engineering of smart cities, in october-november 2023 and 2024. These experimental activities were instrumental both in gaining new inputs and insights for the EMC2 project and to start disseminating this new 15mC model among the future generation of urban practitioners.

Outcomes from WP3, WP4, and WP5 could foster greater engagement with local urban stakeholders beyond those already participating in the consortium. Researchers will assess opportunities for collaboration in this direction in Years 2 and 3.

However, experimental approaches such as urban living labs were not part of the original research proposal and would require additional human resources. A future, innovation-focused project on the EMC2 model could pave the way for deeper involvement in urban living labs.

4. DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION ACTIVITIES

Please describe in what way you promoted dissemination and implementation of the results to the scientific community, policymakers, urban actors as well as citizens/general public and in what way you created new market opportunities?

4.1 Description of dissemination / communication activities (max. 1.5 pages)

Highlight your most important dissemination or communication activities (1 to 3 activities) and how they have contributed to achieving your project goals in more detail. Write the text as a short story:

- **Introduction**
- **What has been done concretely?**
- **Result(s) from these actions**

[INFO: If applicable, please include information on the following: Type of activity (see activity types below), website/social media page used, target group(s), number of participants, aim of the activity, what are the main takeaways or resulting effects, describe any impact from your activity obtained through follow-up you did (media reach, feedback, change in perspectives, attitudes, type of users, etc.), next steps or a lesson learned.]

The dissemination and the communication of project outcomes outside of the perimeter of the consortium is the specific objective of WP7 (not dealt with in section 2.2).

Status of implementation 25% (as scheduled): The Website of the project was created. 4 consortium members participated in the DUT kick-off event in Brussels (April 2024). Consortium members participated in seven important international conferences to disseminate first project results: ECTQG 2023 (European Colloquium of Theoretical and Quantitative Geography), ISUF 2023 and 2024 (International Seminar on Urban Form), SSS 2024 (Space Syntax Symposium), ICCSA 2024 (International Conference of Computer Science and its Applications), AESOP 2024 (conference of the Association of European Schools of Planning) and EAUH 2024 (conference of the European Association for Urban History). Two symposia were organized with urban actors (City of Vienna) and master students at TUW, with the participation of members from CNRS-ESPACE. Consortium members also participated in other dissemination/communication activities not specifically organized within the project (see section 4.2).

Main results: 9 presentations and abstracts at ECTQG 2023, ISUF 2023, ISUF 2024 (x2), SSS 2024, ICCSA 2024, AESOP 2024 and EAUH 2024 (x2). 2 papers in conference proceedings (AESOP 2024 and ICCSA 2024) with a best paper award (ICCSA 2024). 1 poster at the DUT kick-off.

Deliverables of the period:

D 7.1 Launch of the Website of the project. Done and accessible at <https://emc2-dut.org/>

We highlight that an important effort of dissemination and communication is programmed for year 3 through the organization of 4 national dissemination initiatives in Austria, France, Italy and Sweden (D7.2-7.5 scheduled for months 25-36).

4.2 Provide statistical data on your dissemination / communication activities

In reference to chapter 4.1, please specify the (estimated) number of dissemination and communication activities linked to your project for each of the following categories. For the evaluation it is important that you only enter numbers:

Communication activities

- Event (conference, meeting, workshop, internet debate, round table, group discussion, etc.): participation to DUT Kick-off Meeting (Brussels, April 11th-12th 2024) with 1 poster and 1 video; participation to 1 public event (La Ville Nouveaux Horizons, Nov 2023) with 1 presentation; organization of 3 symposia (Vienna Jan 29th-30th 2024, Vienna June 20th-21st 2024, Avignon June 29th 2024) with researchers, students and urban actors.
- Exhibition: Klicken oder tippen Sie hier, um Text einzugeben.
- Interview: 1 radio interview (Radio Bleue Azur, Nov 17th 2023)
- Media article: Klicken oder tippen Sie hier, um Text einzugeben.
- Newsletter : Klicken oder tippen Sie hier, um Text einzugeben.
- Print materials (brochure, leaflet, posters, stickers, banners, etc.): 1 poster for the DUT Kick-off Meeting (April 2024)
- Social media : Klicken oder tippen Sie hier, um Text einzugeben.
- TV / radio campaign: Klicken oder tippen Sie hier, um Text einzugeben.
- Press release: Klicken oder tippen Sie hier, um Text einzugeben.
- Other communication activities: [Website of the project \(https://emc2-dut.org/\)](https://emc2-dut.org/)

Dissemination activities

- Clustering activities: Klicken oder tippen Sie hier, um Text einzugeben.
- Collaboration with EU-funded projects: Klicken oder tippen Sie hier, um Text einzugeben.
- Conferences: Participation to 7 international scientific conferences (ECTQG 2023, ISUF 2023 and 2024, SSS 2024, ICCSA 2024, AESOP 2024 and EAUH 2024) with 9 presentations and 2 papers proceedings
- Education and training events: organization of 6 teaching modules for master students related to the emc2 project (TUWien, Université Côte d'Azur).
- Meetings: organization of 1 group discussion (CNRS-ESPACE/AUA/ADULM June 25th 2024) between researchers and urban actors.
- Other scientific collaboration: Klicken oder tippen Sie hier, um Text einzugeben.

Specify the (estimated) number of persons reached, in the context of all dissemination and communication activities, in each of the following categories:

- Industry, business partners: 10 (within the IMREDD Institute of Innovation and Partnership of Université Côte d'Azur, France).
- Innovators: Klicken oder tippen Sie hier, um Text einzugeben.
- Investors: Klicken oder tippen Sie hier, um Text einzugeben.
- EU Institutions: Klicken oder tippen Sie hier, um Text einzugeben.
- National authorities: Klicken oder tippen Sie hier, um Text einzugeben.
- Regional authorities: Klicken oder tippen Sie hier, um Text einzugeben.
- Local authorities: Klicken oder tippen Sie hier, um Text einzugeben.
- Civil society: Klicken oder tippen Sie hier, um Text einzugeben.
- Citizens: Klicken oder tippen Sie hier, um Text einzugeben.
- Research communities: Participation to 7 international scientific conferences (ECTQG 2023, ISUF 2023 and 2024, SSS 2024, ICCSA 2024, AESOP 2024 and EAUH 2024) reaching app. 500 people.
- Specific end user communities: Klicken oder tippen Sie hier, um Text einzugeben.
- International organisation (UN body, OECD, etc.): Klicken oder tippen Sie hier, um Text einzugeben.
- Other: Klicken oder tippen Sie hier, um Text einzugeben.

5. OUTLOOK (max. 1 page)

Only for annual reports:

Describe the work planned for the next reporting period, structured according to the work packages. Discuss envisaged changes as compared to the original work plan, if any, reflecting the deficiencies, risks and bottlenecks described in Chapter 2.2.

Only for final reports:

➤ **Follow-up Investments and Opportunities**

Based on your previous responses in the Online Survey (under *Follow-up Activities*), how has your participation in the DUT Partnership:

- **Facilitated further investments or funding opportunities to expand your project activities?**
- **Created follow-up opportunities with new partners, organisations, or networks?**
- **Opened new perspectives or innovative approaches that could help transform urban areas?**

➤ **Impact on Future Research and Innovation (R&I) Work**

What has been the most beneficial impact of participating in the DUT Partnership on your future research and innovation work? Please consider aspects, such as:

- **Enhanced knowledge, expertise, or capacity-building for future projects.**
- **New collaborations, partnerships, or networks that have emerged.**
- **Any other significant outcomes that you attribute to your involvement with the DUT Partnership.**

The second year of the research project will be pivotal in advancing our scheduled activities. We plan to conclude WP2 (Assessment of the potential of EMC2 in metropolitan areas) and WP3 (Study of historical formation), fully engage in WP4 (Analysis of relations with mobility and blue/green networks) and WP5 (Usage analysis, 3D models, and test area projects), and initiate WP6 (Generalization of findings and guidelines). WP1 (Development and assessment of the theoretical model) will be temporarily paused and resumed in year 3. The main adjustment to the original timeline will be the extension of WP2 until month 21, while taking advantage of the early start of WP5, which was launched in year 1. A detailed breakdown of the planned activities for each work package is provided below.

WP1. Pause within year 2, however outcomes from WPs 2, 3, 4 and 5 will be constantly used to enrich the dialogue with urban stakeholders on the specification of the EMC2 model.

WP2: In the early months of year 2, researchers will finalize the analytical protocols for identifying foreground street networks and assessing built-up forms and services on these networks. All protocols will be completed and applied to the five European metropolitan areas within month 18, enabling researchers to fully identify and characterize the supporting mesh of the EMC2 model in these study areas. Additionally, the test areas will be validated in collaboration with urban stakeholders, with particular attention to the distinct challenges these test areas pose within the broader supporting mesh. Deliverables and Milestones scheduled for year 2:

D2.4bis Analytical protocol to identify the bridging ties within the system. This is a new deliverable added to the original plan, in order to complement deliverable 2.4 (month 15)

D2.5 Maps of results of the application of protocols to the metropolitan areas (moved from month 14 to 18, but maps of accessible population already produced)

M6 Completed Identification of supporting mesh of the EMC2 model in metropolitan areas and of potential to act as main streets (moved from month 14 to 18)

M7 Validation of test areas based on metropolitan-wide analysis with stakeholders (from month 15 to 18)

D2.6 Draft journal paper on combined protocols and comparative analysis (moved from month 18 to 21)

WP3. Year 2 will also mark the completion of WP3, with the identification of the evolutionary processes behind the observed forms in the test areas and the assessment of their development potential (Milestone 8). The diachronic analysis of street networks in metropolitan areas will be enhanced by the inclusion of Versilia, in addition to the already planned case studies of Gothenburg and Vienna.

Deliverables scheduled for year 2:

D 3.2 Morphogenetic diagram/maps of the chosen test areas (month 15)

D 3.3 Working paper on diachronic analysis of street networks in selected metro areas (month 18)

D 3.4 Working paper on assessment of the evolutive potential of test areas (month 18)

D 3.5 Draft journal paper on historic analysis (month 24)

WP4. This WP will enter in its most productive phase, with key deliverables scheduled for year 2. We foresee some delay in the deliverables because the recruitment of the PhD researcher at Chalmers took more time than anticipated.

Deliverables scheduled for year 2:

D4.1 Analytical protocol of interaction between the EMC2 model and the green/blue networks (month 21 instead of 15)

D4.2 Maps of assessed potential mobility flows in test areas of Versilia (month 15)

D4.3 Code of the agent-based human behavior and mobility model in the EMC2 (month 21)

D4.4 Integrated assessment of planning scenarios in Gothenburg concerning green/blue networks (month 30 instead of 24)

WP5. Like WP4, WP5 will enter its most productive phase. An important milestone will be reached in month 21, with the completion of fieldwork in all selected test areas. Other key deliverables will be:

D5.1 Maps of public/private interfaces, functions and public space organization of the test areas (m 18)

D5.2 Ethograms of human usage of test areas and correlation with morpho-functional features (m 21)

D5.3 Numeric 3D-models of main streets in their present situation (month 24)

WP6. The start of WP6 is foreseen for month 18 and will involve close collaboration within the four research teams and the four urban authorities within the consortium. By the end of year 2, a key deliverable, whose collective validation with stakeholders is also a milestone, is the document of assessment guidelines of the EMC2 potential at metropolitan and local scale.

6. PROJECT ORGANISATION AND MANAGEMENT *(no page limit)*

Please provide information on coordination activities during the reporting period, such as communication between project participants, possible cooperation with other projects etc.

Have changes occurred in terms of project organisation and management in the reporting period?

NO

Within the project organization, a transversal work package (WP8) has the objective to ensure efficient management of the project. The first year was marked by significant efforts in establishing both the administrative and scientific infrastructure. Specifically:

- A kick-off meeting was held in Nice from November 9th-11th, 2023, with the participation of 20 colleagues from CNRS-ESPACE, Urban Design TUW, DESTeC-Univ. Pisa, SMoG-Univ. Chalmers, and AUA.
- Two General Assemblies were convened on November 9th, 2023, and March 13th, 2024.
- Steering Committee meetings were held on an almost monthly basis (Oct 10th, Dec 18th, 2023; Jan 22nd, Feb 22nd, Mar 20th, Apr 18th, July 23rd, Sept 6th, and Oct 23rd, 2024).

The project leader is responsible for organizing and recording minutes of General Assemblies and Steering Committee meetings, managing participant feedback, and storing all documents on the project platform.

Beyond the kick-off meeting, the first year's key milestones included:

1. The drafting and signing of the Consortium Agreement (April 2024).
2. The drafting of the first version of the Data Management Plan (June 2024).

Regarding research infrastructure, a shared platform for project data and documents was created through CNRS's Humanum platform, providing a secure, high-capacity shared space (Sharedocs) accessible to all project members.

In terms of human resources, year 1 saw the recruitment of 4 postdoctoral researchers (at ESPACE-CNRS, DESTeC, and SMoG, 25% women), 6 PhD candidates (at ESPACE-CNRS/AUA, DESTeC, SMoG, and UD-TUW, 67% women), and 2 interns (at ESPACE-CNRS, 50% women).

The drafting and negotiation of the Consortium Agreement posed particular challenges for the representatives in different countries but was greatly facilitated by technical support from the CNRS Regional Delegation on the French Riviera.

A specific difficulty the Consortium must manage throughout the project is a slight misalignment in the official start dates. Administratively and financially, the project began on October 1st, 2023, for partners in Austria and Sweden, but on November 1st, 2023, for partners in France and Italy. This discrepancy also affects the period covered by this report: October 1st, 2023, to October 31st, 2024, corresponding to 12 months of activities for French and Italian partners but 13 months for Austrian and Swedish partners.

7. YOUR COMMENTS FOR THE DUT PARTNERSHIP *(no page limit)*

Do you have any comments for the DUT Partnership?

Klicken oder tippen Sie hier, um Text einzugeben.

8. ELECTRONIC SIGNATURE

This report is fully agreed among all partners of the project.

Date: 07.11.2024

Name of coordinator: Giovanni FUSCO

9. FORMALITIES CHECKLIST

- All sections of this reporting template must be filled in and answered.
- Please submit the Project Progress Report / Final Project Report in .pdf format via the Online Project Monitoring System accessible at: <https://ffg.countit.at/#/login>
- In case of questions with regard to this reporting template, please send an email to the **Projects Contact Point:** projects@dutpartnership.eu

 Please note that you can only fill in the form fields, all other content is blocked. For automatic evaluation purposes, please ensure that you submit the report as a **Word document**. You can submit a pdf in addition.